

ZnFe₂O₄@Co₃O₄/X zeolite: A novel magnetic recoverable nanocomposite for the sonocatalytic degradation of rhodamine B (RhB) dye

Meysam Sadeghi

Department of Chemistry, Lorestan University, Khorramabad, Iran
Email: meysamsadeghi1364@gmail.com

Maryam Gholami

Department of Chemistry, Lorestan University, Khorramabad, Iran
Email: Maryam.gholami78@yahoo.com

Pourya Zarshenas

Faculty of Chemistry & Petroleum Sciences, Shahid Beheshti University (SBU), Iran
Email: dr.pouryazarshenas@yahoo.com

Abstract

Highly efficient and effective remediation of toxic organic dye sewages are a major dilemma in the industries. In this work, the novel ZnFe₂O₄@Co₃O₄/X zeolite nanocomposite was successfully fabricated and applied for the rhodamine B (RhB) dye in water media. The as-fabricated ZnFe₂O₄@Co₃O₄/X zeolite nanocomposite was identified via FESEM, EDAX, FTIR, XRD and VSM analyses. Several parameters such as irradiation time, initial dye concentration, process type, catalyst dosage, organic dye and type H₂O₂ concentration have been evaluated to attain the maximum sonocatalytic efficiency. Regarding the obtained results, the ZnFe₂O₄@Co₃O₄/X zeolite sonocatalyst was incredibly able to completely degrade this dye by the ultrasonic and H₂O₂. The free ·OH radicals were recognized as the main active species on the RhB degradation under US irradiation. Additionally, the reproducibility of the ZnFe₂O₄@Co₃O₄/X sonocatalyst was investigated, which affirmed that it can be reused up to four runs with almost trivial loss of catalytic activity. Additionally, the sonodegradation of RhB by the ZnFe₂O₄@Co₃O₄/X zeolite sonocatalyst in the presence of US/H₂O₂ system reveals a great activity to investigate highly removal of organic contaminants from wastewater.

Keywords: ZnFe₂O₄@Co₃O₄/X, Zeolite, Nanocomposite, rhodamine B (RhB), Degradation.